

Teens grow up in development hemoglobin of the amount effect

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Abstract: Hemoglobin, sugar in diseases average quantity change with depends respectively modern of medicine in development important have has been from parameters is one Hemoglobin in sugar erythrocytes by oxygen and for transport in carbon dioxide is used and energy transmission according to sugar oxygenates. This in the article teenagers grow up in development hemoglobin of the amount effect learning about scientific research results brought passed.

Key words: hemoglobin, blood rotation system, erythrocytes, growth period, protein, sugar quantity,

Introduction: Oils growth and development for hemoglobin quantity very important Hemoglobin, red blood in the cells located protein molecules set These are molecules transport oxygen with busy, to a teenager arrived came oxygen the amount to get help will give.

Teens growth and in development hemoglobin of the amount effect while so that is sufficient level hemoglobin in the absence of oxygen arrived did not come because of growth and development problem to be can And this young people and necessary of the elements deprived was in humans anemia (blood lack of) cause will be

From this except, of loss high level to be hemoglobin of the amount effect shows. High loss level the air of oxygen concentration decrease possible and this while hemoglobin of molecules that it does not transport oxygen reason will be

Also some Dangerous means (for example, nicotine) and hemoglobin normal functioning of molecules on time Dangerous effect in the form of to grow effect to do can

These are with together, genetic factors are also hemoglobin the amount effect to reach can Some in humans genetic regimes presence because of hemoglobin molecule structure differently will be and this while oxygen transport effect is enough

Many people in cases, hemoglobin quantity normally when Teenagers growth and development for enough level if not necessarily it's not. In this of a person eating mode, external environment condition and another a lot factors are also important role execution to reach can

Main part : teens development and growth for more oxygen to the necessity have Hemoglobin while of blood in transporting oxygen important role plays teens

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development and hemoglobin of the amount effect while each other strong way effect is enough If one of a person hemoglobin if the amount is low , it high level active or sports practices with engage in for necessary has been oxygen enough level does not pass . And this of ointments development and activity limits Also hemoglobin quantity many p if it is while your blood oxygen environment improve and teenagers strong way to develop help will give . Such in cases , hemoglobin of the amount to be checked and right level storage important as well treatment there are also requirements will be Hemoglobin is red blood liver protein molecule in the cell . These are molecules oxygen transports the amount and him the body tall delivers Also they carbon dioxide the body inside to organs take it is also important to go role plays

In children in the blood hemoglobin norm the following in the table given .

Your child age	Hemoglobin norm (g/l)
1-3 days	145-225
1 week old	135-215
2 weeks old	125-205
1 month old	100-180
2 months old	90-140
3-6 months old	95-135
6 months - 1 year	100-140
1-2 years old	105-145
3-6 years old	110-150
7-12 years old	115-150
13-15 years old	115-155
16-18 years old	120-160

Tenns growth and in development hemoglobin quantity very important Enough amount of hemoglobin to be the body for necessary in oxygen transport and

the body inside oxygen the amount in providing important If hemoglobin If the amount is low , the body inside oxygen quantity less to be possible and then the body temporarily to weakness face coming can

In children or grower in humans hemoglobin level low to anemia take coming can And this energy level down your activity and of studies development effect to do can

In children hemoglobin level increase and him improve for to be need has been proteins , minerals , and another necessary elements with depends institutions take will go Such in cases , health improve for , manure with strong eating and doctor recommendation based on necessary from therapy use need One how many in cases , high hemoglobin level is also harmful to be because it is possible this of blood right rotation effect to do can That's why for , hemoglobin level check and him normalization for certain amount water to drink and salty foods less consumption to do it is necessary In general when , hemoglobin quantity of a person common health and development for very is important and him right measure , problem and problems prevention get for need Hemoglobin in the decrease red fish , red caviar , eggs yellow , sea products foodie to do good benefit will give . This of products contained of iron about 11 percent organism by will be used .

If health with dependent serious problems or blood diseases otherwise , in the blood hemoglobin quickly increase difficulty does not give birth . Another one the blood breeder product this namatak fruits From him tincture preparation need will be One a handful namatak to the fruits one liter boiling water put in a thermos one yesterday is silenced . In the morning tincture swim taken and burned according to honey is added . This drink children and adults for one kind of is useful . From eating before per day one how many times this tincture half from a glass to drink need In anemia coffee and drink bitter tea recommendation will not be done . These are drinks in the composition from our orgasm iron and calcium wash emits substances exist None if not , in the blood hemoglobin increase measures being viewed during them restriction need

Summary teens grow up in development hemoglobin of the amount effect conclusion about more information give can Fructose , kind of one how many organic molecule mostly fertility and in the processes of gluconeogenesis participation is enough Summary supply grow up in development important important have being , this molecule energy in providing important role plays

Hemoglobin quantity grow up also important in development important have is because hemoglobin of a teenager high in the amount transports oxygen and so by doing energetic of processes process for necessary will be teens development during

hemoglobin of the amount high to be energy work in release and from the attack protection doer functions in execution important Summary and hemoglobin quantity the following factors with effect to find can :

That's right nutrition : Good eating lighter Taminos with is filled from foods consists of to be need

- Vitamin and minerals : teens when developed vitamins and minerals Demand will be their enough supply good to be need
- Ishrak Methods : Physics action indicators done don't increase through energy spending the most good road is considered
- Good participation : of blood accuracy storage for water supply very important
- From birth after Diseases : If from birth after patients appear if it is hemoglobin the amount the effect is more dangerous will be

All this to factors attention if given , conclusion and hemoglobin to the amount attention when looking grow up development pull for necessary things over work can

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